

引入情境控制来管理发展经济对象和系统

INTRODUCTION OF SITUATIONAL CONTROLLING TO MANAGE DEVELOPMENT ECONOMIC OBJECTS AND SYSTEMS

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抽象的。在制裁限制条件下提高管理经济对象和系统发展的效率似乎是相关的。选择治理机构促进经济目标和系统发展的活动作为研究对象。研究的主题是态势管理信息系统。研究的目的是证实需要将态势管理信息系统引入经济对象和系统的活动中,并在其组成中包括态势控制子系统。所提出方法的实际实施将提高经济对象和系统的效率。

关键词: 经济对象和系统、发展、管理、信息系统、态势控制。

Abstract. *Increasing the efficiency of managing the development of economic objects and systems under the conditions of sanctions restrictions seems relevant. The activities of governing bodies for the development of economic objects and systems were chosen as the object of study. The subject of the study is the situational management information system. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the need to introduce a situational management information system into the activities of economic objects and systems and include a situational controlling subsystem in its composition. The practical implementation of the proposed approaches will improve the efficiency of economic objects and systems.*

Keywords: *economic objects and systems, development, management, information system, situational controlling.*

Introduction

Despite the fact that the concept of situational management is a relatively new area of economic science, today it is actively developing and is widely used at different levels of management. This concept is intended to substantiate management decisions in relation to the functioning of complex economic objects and systems in market conditions. It is based on the principles of situational controlling with

the inclusion of procedures for goal setting and managing the process of achieving them. According to the authors, the application of the concept of situational management most fully satisfies the requirements and promising directions for the development and implementation of strategic programs for the development of economic objects and systems.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the need to introduce a situational management information system into the activities of economic objects and systems and include a situational controlling subsystem in its composition.

Materials and methods

Traditional approaches to managing the development of economic objects and systems were based on the principles of formalization and simplification. Of course, with a decrease in the number of parameters, it is much easier to control an object or system. Many control technologies that until recently seemed modern were formed based on the principle of minimizing parameters. But today in management the role of the influence of environmental factors on the object of management has increased significantly. This circumstance is recognized by most economists [1, 3].

With the growing volumes of processed information and the need to take into account an increasing number of factors of external influence on the development of economic objects and systems, the complexity of analyzing and modeling their management increases. Therefore, in modern conditions, new approaches are needed to formalize the impact of environmental factors on the control object. But, as practice shows, the influence of environmental factors on an object most often cannot be predicted in advance [2, 6]. At the same time, it can be considered fair to say that the control object is not influenced by the entire environment, but only by those factors that can be formalized as an information situation. The need to take into account the influence of such a situation on the control object, its condition and development dynamics led to the introduction of the concept of situational management [4, 7].

In theoretical terms, situational management is used as an alternative to planned management. It allows you to manage the development of economic objects and systems under unforeseen circumstances and/or in emergency situations (abnormal situation management, ASM) [8]. Approaches to situational management of emergency situations are closely related to competitive decision-making factors, such as capital investments, technological risks, the domestic market and its infrastructure, the political environment, and strategies for the development of economic objects and systems [5].

Situational management can be defined as a system of concepts, models and rules for interpreting, analyzing and predicting the development of the state of a

control object. Such situations exist in dynamic systems for managing the development of economic objects and systems during predetermined time intervals [5]. To manage situations, multi-agent systems, correlative analysis, metaheuristics, situational management information systems, etc. are used. In this article we will consider an approach to the use of information systems for situational management of the development of economic objects and systems.

Results and discussion

In theoretical terms, the basis for the formation of an information system for situational management (ISSM) of the development process of economic objects and systems is based on a hypothesis that assumes that all economic information necessary for management, previously used in an unstructured form, can be structured on the basis of a special image. Bottoms and generalizations using formalization procedures in specific areas of regional management. The central element of such a system is the situation that determines the current state of the control object, taking into account the impact of environmental factors on it, and also provides for the dynamics of their change over time. At the same time, it is important to observe the need and possibility of representing in time the target or required states of the control object and the corresponding expected states of environmental factors. In other words, each specific state of the environment (current state of the market) must correspond to the required (target) state of the control object.

It seems obvious that in economic situational control systems, the current and target situations in which the control object is located under the influence of environmental factors must differ. In the general case, these situations are determined by a certain set of economic indicators that characterize the state of the control object in relation to a specific situation. The difference between the indicators of an acceptable typical (generalized) current situation and a typical target situation will be called the reference situation of the control object. This makes it possible to match each reference situation with certain management activities. Carrying out these activities allows you to eliminate the differences between the current and target problem situations of the control object under given or previously known environmental conditions.

The above circumstances make it possible to define a model of situational management of the development of economic objects and systems by the following components:

- 1) a set of target situations, determined by a set of economic indicators and reflecting a discrete process of changing the state of the regional economy in continuous time with a given (planned) course of its development process;
- 2) current and reference states of the environment, which can accompany, respectively, the actual and planned states of development of the regional economy;
- 3) a set of reference situations and corresponding environmental states that arise regardless of the control object, but have a significant impact on it.

In this case, each pair “reference situation - state of the environment” is associated with certain organizational and managerial measures, which, under given environmental conditions, make it possible to achieve the required state of the control object, determined by the program of its strategic development. To reduce the total number of target, current and reference situations, when describing them, it is proposed to use the apparatus of fuzzy sets, which allows for a generalized representation of various situations in terms of natural language.

In its structural design, the information system for situational management of the development of economic objects and systems in the most general case can be presented in the form of a diagram shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Situational management information system of development of economic objects and systems.

The information system for situational management of the development of economic objects and systems functions as follows. In the Time Counting Subsystem, after the planned period of time has elapsed, a control signal is generated. When it appears in the *Current Information Collection Subsystem*, primary processing of data is performed that determines:

- current (actual) state of the control object;
- the state of the process of economic development of economic objects and systems (consumer demand, resource and production capabilities of enterprises, their financial, technical and technological state of the enterprise, etc.);

- the current state of environmental factors (inflation level, interest rate of banks, level of competition, investment rating of economic objects and systems, etc.).

Based on the information received, the current situation is formed, which determines the actual state of the control object and the nature of the impact of environmental factors. Next, the situation formed in this way is submitted to the *Situation Comparison Subsystem*. At the same time, the required (target) state of the control object at a given moment in time is supplied to the same subsystem from the knowledge base. After this, all differences between the actual and required situations of the control object are determined. If there are no differences, then the process of functioning of the control object proceeds as planned. Otherwise, the pair “*Indicators of differences between the current and reference states of the control object*” - “*Characteristics of the impact of environmental factors*” is formed. Based on the resulting pair, the reference situation closest to it in content is identified in the knowledge base. In accordance with this situation, a set of necessary organizational and managerial measures is determined, the implementation of which will eliminate the identified differences between the actual and required state of the control object. To check the feasibility of the selected activities, the mathematical apparatus of queuing theory can be used. The results of the check in the form of the newly received current state of the control object are transmitted to the *information collection subsystem* (the transmission connection and its direction are shown in Fig. 1 with a dotted line). If the newly obtained situation shows that the selected measures allow one to get closer to achieving the given goal, then these organizational and managerial measures are implemented directly at the control object.

After completing the selected activities, the information system moves on to the next management cycle, implemented according to the principle described above, etc., until a satisfactory result is obtained, i.e. until there is no difference between the actual situation and the required one.

Further development of the information system for situational management of the development of economic objects and systems is associated with the implementation of the *Situational Controlling Subsystem*. This *subsystem* takes into account the specific operating conditions of economic objects and systems in commodity markets, as well as environmental factors and the nature of their impact on the management object. It allows you to implement financial and economic management functions that ensure the adoption of operational and strategic management decisions. Situational controlling, along with other latest management tools, helps the management of economic entities and systems to ensure accelerated progress in the development of all areas of their activities.

In general, situational controlling should be understood as a functionally separate direction of the economic work of management bodies of economic objects

and systems. It is associated with the implementation of the financial and economic management function in the form of a situation for making operational and strategic decisions and issuing recommendations that determine the reasons for changes in the analyzed situations and aimed at eliminating them.

The main goal of situational controlling is to orient the management process towards achieving all the goals facing the management object by using previously accumulated experience of functioning in various situations of a problematic environment. At the same time, its main functions are:

- 1) regulation of the activities of the management apparatus to achieve the goals of economic objects and systems in accordance with external and internal operating conditions;
- 2) information and intellectual support for making management decisions;
- 3) creation and ensuring the functioning of a general information system for managing the development of economic objects and systems based on a knowledge base;
- 4) ensuring the optimality and rationality of the management process.

Thus, the basic concept of situational controlling includes procedures for defining goals and managing their achievement.

The formation of the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* is based on the further development of the automated control system by the development of economic objects and systems, which should reflect in a formalized form all existing experience in monitoring and managing their activities. To implement this approach, it is necessary to develop and include in the automated control system many rules for the formation of logical conclusions, having the following structure: “the current state of the external and internal environment of the business entity the reasons for the occurrence of deviations of the actual values of the parameters from the planned ones.”

At the same time, the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* clearly defines the goals of economic development of the management object, management principles and methods of their implementation. Occupying a special place in the automated control system, the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* will provide information support for decision-making in order to optimally use existing opportunities, and realistically assess the strengths and weaknesses of the activities of economic objects and systems.

It should be noted that the need to implement the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* in the Information Management System for the development of economic objects and systems today is becoming an objective need. Most economic entities and systems experience difficulties in selling their products both on the foreign and domestic markets. Market prices for various types of equipment, materials, and rental premises usually grow faster than prices for already produced prod-

ucts. This leads to a decrease in the profits of economic objects and systems when selling their products, which entails the need for a detailed analysis of the market and the importance of solving the problem - what, where, from whom and at what price to buy. All this creates additional prerequisites for the implementation of the *Situational Controlling Subsystem*, which allows you to find the most optimal course of action, maintain and increase the market share of regional products, and achieve maximum profits for business entities.

The introduction of a situational controlling subsystem is actually an innovation. Its widespread use at the regional level is necessary for the following reasons:

1) the use of situational controlling is an extremely effective method of market management, which requires minor adaptation to the specific conditions of the activity of economic objects and systems;

2) analysis of emerging problems in managing the development of economic objects and systems, their trends and experience in eliminating them is important for a timely assessment of emerging difficulties and finding ways to overcome them;

3) the introduction of a situational controlling subsystem will allow the prompt application of the most modern management methods, since the main thing in controlling is the implementation today of what will be used only tomorrow, relying on previously accumulated operational experience, which allows us to determine trends in further economic development;

4) in the practical implementation of situational controlling procedures, all its components (accounting, analysis, planning, control, marketing, information) and their deep knowledge, a reasonable combination and interrelation of which ensures high efficiency in the development of economic objects and systems;

5) situational controlling is aimed at the future, therefore it is one of the foundations of strategic management of the development of economic objects and systems;

6) using the accumulated management experience, situational controlling actively promotes the constant improvement of the qualifications of all employees of management bodies for the development of economic objects and systems.

However, for the successful application of situational control in modern Russian conditions, it is necessary to solve the following main problems.

Firstly, for the actual implementation of situational controlling, it is necessary to rebuild the accounting, planning and analysis system used both at the regional level and at the level of individual enterprises.

Secondly, when switching to a situational controlling system, an important requirement is the use of management accounting as the basis for the accounting policy of all business entities. To do this, it is necessary not only to divide costs into fixed and variable, to identify profit volumes, but also to take into account

costs and sales results both by type of product, service, and by market segments, customer groups, and places where production and financial results are formed.

The widespread introduction of situational controlling allows the use of the most modern management methods in competition and promotes innovation. The simultaneous introduction of the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* into the activities of management bodies of economic objects and systems will allow solving the following problems:

- overcome the inconsistency of management decisions in relation to different levels of management;
- improve the organization of management of the development of economic objects and systems by applying best practices and the latest management principles;
- improve coordination of the activities of management bodies of economic objects and systems;
- rationally combine management influences at all levels of management;
- solve a lot of specific problems of managing the development of economic objects and systems;
- development of progressive schemes and methods of connecting science with the activities of economic objects and systems.

Conclusion.

The results obtained during the research allow us to draw the following conclusions.

1. The introduction of modern information management systems for the development of economic objects and systems is an objective necessity for solving complex management problems in difficult to predict situations.

2. With information influence, the information situation acts as a shell in relation to the control object. This approach allows you to reduce the information load on the control object. Practice shows that in some cases it is quite enough to control the situation, and not the object itself.

3. The use of information management systems for the development of economic objects and systems opens up the possibility of implementing flexible management, which makes their activities more sustainable compared to deterministic management.

4. ISSM make it possible to differentiate the management resources of economic objects and systems in relation to specific information situations. This improves resource efficiency.

5. The introduction of the *Situational Controlling Subsystem* within the framework of the Information Management System will have a positive impact not only on the development of economic objects and systems, but will also allow them to promptly respond to market changes, act on it, constantly focusing on the future,

determine the prospects for their development through effective planning with direct and feedback, achieve high financial results and not be afraid for your future.

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